

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EPILEPSY: ETIOLOGY, PATHOGENESIS, SYMPTOMS, TREATMENT AND PREVENTION

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Abstract

Epilepsy is a condition marked by abnormal neuronal discharges or hyperexcitability of neurons with synchronicity and is recognized as a major public health concern. The pathology is categorized into three subgroups: acquired, idiopathic, and epilepsy of genetic or developmental origin. There are approximately 1000 associated genes and the role of γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) mediated inhibition, as well as glutamate mediated excitation, forms the basis of pathology. Epilepsy is further classified as being of focal, general or unknown onset. Genetic predisposition, comorbidities and novel biomarkers are useful for prediction. Prevalent postictal symptoms are postictal headache and migraine, postictal psychosis and delirium, postictal Todd's paresis and postictal automatisms. Diagnostic methods include electroencephalography (EEG), computed tomography scan, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), positron emission tomography, single photon emission computed tomography and genetic testing; EEG and MRI are the two main techniques. Clinical history and witness testimonies combined with a knowledge of seizure semiology helps in distinguishing between seizures. Clinical information and patient history do not always lead to a clear diagnosis, in which case EEG and 24-hour EEG monitoring with video recording (video-EEG/vEEG) help in seizure differentiation. Treatment includes first aid, therapeutics such as anti-epileptic drugs, surgery, ketogenic diet and gene therapy. In this review, we are focusing on summarizing published literature on epilepsy and epileptic seizures, and concisely apprise the reader of the latest cutting-edge advances and knowledge on epileptic seizures.

Keywords: Epilepsy etiology, pathophysiological mechanisms, epilepsy treatment.

Introduction

Epilepsy is one of the most common neurological conditions, affecting over 70 million people worldwide (1). Its prevalence in high-income countries is estimated to be 6.4 cases per 1,000 persons, and the annual incidence is 67.8 cases per 100,000 person-years (2). These numbers are almost quadrupled in low-income and middle-income countries (LMICs). The disease is caused by many genetic and acquired factors, some of which are reviewed here. According to the International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE), epilepsy is diagnosed when someone has two unprovoked seizures occurring more than 24 h apart; or when someone has a single unprovoked seizure (if recurrence risk is high); or when a diagnosis of an epilepsy syndrome is done (3). An epileptic seizure is defined as a transient behavioral change that might present objective signs or subjective symptoms (such as loss of awareness, stiffening, a sensation that rises from the abdomen to the chest, an odd smell, etc.), caused by abnormal excessive or synchronous neuronal activity in the brain (4).

Etiology of epilepsy and pathophysiological mechanisms

Seizures and epilepsy are the consequence of an imbalance between excitation and inhibition within certain regions of the central nervous system (CNS).

Given the numerous mechanisms that control neuronal electrical function, there are many different ways to perturb this balance, and therefore many different causes of both seizures and epilepsy. The ILAE Task Force (5) has defined six etiologic categories for epilepsy: genetic, structural, metabolic, infectious, immune, and unknown. These are not hierarchical, and a patient's epilepsy may be classified into more than one etiologic category.

Structural etiology

A structural etiology refers to an abnormal finding on neuroimaging reasonably inferred to cause the patient's seizures with concordant electroclinical assessments and/or clinical findings (6, 7). Structural etiologies may be acquired or genetic. Acquired structural causes include hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy, stroke, trauma, and infection. Genetic origins belong to a broad range of disorders ranging from single-nucleotide mutations such as missense, frameshift and non-sense mutations, copy number variations by *de novo* or inherited DNA deletion or duplication, to chromosomal copy number abnormalities (8).

Among structural etiologies, it is noteworthy the relatively frequent finding of hippocampal sclerosis (HS) in mesial temporal lobe seizures (5). The characteristic pathological findings of HS consist of loss of

pyramidal neurons and gliosis occurring primarily in the dentate hilus (CA4 subregion) and CA1 subregion with less change in the CA3 subregion. The resulting loss of inhibitory gamma-aminobutyric acid neurons (GABA-ergic) and neuropeptidergic hilar interneurons and the degeneration of excitatory mossy cells induces a synaptic reorganization primarily consistent in mossy fiber sprouting (granule cell axon sprouting) which predominantly projects into the inner molecular layer and hilar region and might establish excitatory feedback loops with the soma and dendrites of normal and ectopic granule cells (9). Mossy fiber sprouting is also linked to granule cell neurogenesis which is acutely accelerated shortly after the epileptogenic insult partly due to a loss of reelin expression by injured hippocampal interneurons (10, 11).

Finally, reactive gliosis induces the downregulation of gap junction connexins, glutamate transporters, potassium channels and aquaporin 4 channels, and also promotes the altered neuronal expression of cation-chloride co-transporters, all of which can promote neuronal network hyperexcitability (12). Activated astrocytes also release gliotransmitters and cytokines, which increase neuronal network synchronization (13).

Genetic etiology

An epilepsy is considered of genetic origin if there is a known, or presumed, specific disease-causing variant in a gene or copy number variant, in which seizures are a common phenotype (5). A study by Wang et al (14) found that 977 genes were associated with epilepsy. The authors classified these genes into 4 categories according to the manifestation of epilepsy in phenotypes. These genes include epilepsy genes (genes that cause epilepsies or syndromes with epilepsy as the core symptom), neurodevelopment-associated epilepsy genes (genes associated with both brain-development malformations and epilepsy), epilepsy-related genes (genes associated with both physical or other systemic abnormalities and epilepsy or seizures) and putatively associated with epilepsy (genes which require further verification) (14). Accordingly, epilepsies can be broadly grouped into three classes defined as genetic generalized epilepsy (GGE), focal epilepsy (FE), and epileptic encephalopathy, with specific syndromes within each class defined by differences in specific seizure types, EEG patterns, age of onset, and disease progression (15).

The GGE syndromes tend to start in childhood or adolescence and are characterized by generalized seizures that involve both sides of the brain (15). They include, among others, juvenile myoclonic epilepsy, and childhood absence epilepsy, in which large recurrent deletions at chromosomes 15q13.3, 16p13.11, and 15q11.2 have been identified (16, 17). With these three deletions, an association with autism and schizophrenia has also been found.

FE originate in one hemisphere of the brain. A few examples of FE syndromes are familial mesial temporal lobe epilepsy (FMTLE), autosomal dominant lateral temporal epilepsy (ADLTE) and autosomal dominant nocturnal frontal lobe epilepsy (ADNFLE). FMTLE was first described as a benign syndrome with prominent psychic and autonomic seizures and no association

with HS or febrile seizures (FS), and as other types of inherited epilepsies, FMTLE is likely to be genetically heterogeneous. Genetic analysis in a four-generation kindred with several affected members from FMTLE detected a group of markers with lod score >3 on chromosome 4q13.2-q21.3 spanning a 7 cM region (18). ADLTE is a form of heritable temporal lobe epilepsy with auditory ictal manifestations. A linkage analysis in a three-generation family with 11 patients identified mutations of the leucine-rich glioma-inactivated 1 (*LGII*) gene at the 10q24 locus (19). ADNFLE has a childhood onset, and it is characterized by brief nocturnal motor seizures with origins in the frontal lobe. This was the first inherited epilepsy syndrome in which a specific mutation has been identified. The gene for this FE, *CHRNA4*, maps to chromosome 20q13 and it encodes the α -4 subunit of the neuronal nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR), which is a pentameric ligand-gated ion channel consisting of α and β subunits. In ADNFLE patients, a missense mutation occurs in this gene causing serine to be replaced with phenylalanine at position 247, a strongly conserved amino acid residue in the second transmembrane domain (20). To better understand the functional significance of this mutation, Kuryatov et al characterized the properties of mutant and wild-type human α 4 β 2 AChRs expressed in *Xenopus* oocytes. The authors found that mutant AChR responses showed faster desensitization, slower recovery from desensitization, less inward rectification, and virtually no Ca^{2+} permeability as compared with wild type α 4 β 2 AChRs. They concluded that the net effect of the mutation is to reduce AChR function

Epileptic encephalopathies are severe, early onset conditions characterized by refractory seizures, developmental delay or regression associated with ongoing epileptic activity, and generally poor prognosis. To this class of epilepsies belong a group of disorders resulting from mutations in genes encoding ion channels, such as *KCNQ2* in benign familial neonatal seizures, *SCN2A* in benign familial infantile epilepsy and *SCN1A* in Dravet syndrome. *KCNQ2* gene encodes voltage-gated potassium channels that produce the M current which, under normal conditions, induce a hyperpolarizing shift in membrane voltage. Loss of its function can increase neuronal hyperexcitability, leading to spontaneous seizure activities as reported in *KCNQ2* knockout mice. *SCN1A* gene encodes the Nav1.1 (one of nine α subtypes of voltage-gated sodium channels preferentially expressed in GABA-ergic neurons), and this is one of the most important causative genes in epilepsy with more than 1,257 epilepsy-related mutations being reported. Dysfunction of Nav1.1 channels lead to reduced excitability of GABA-ergic neurons resulting in brain hyperexcitability in patients with Dravet syndrome. The identification of these monogenic epilepsy-causing genes gave rise to the "channelopathy" hypothesis of epilepsy origin, postulating that dysfunction or dysregulation of ion channels is a common mechanism underlying epilepsy syndromes.

Infectious etiology

Infections of the CNS are a major risk factor for epilepsy, and they are the most common identifiable etiology of epilepsy in some regions of the world. The

reported risk of unprovoked seizures in population-based cohorts of survivors of CNS infections from developed countries is between 6.8 and 8.3 %, and is higher in LMICs.

An infectious etiology refers to a patient with epilepsy, not a patient with seizures due to an acute infection of the CNS. In this context, seizures are induced by brain alterations in response to neurotropic infectious agents that attack the CNS like *cysticercus*, human immunodeficiency virus, cytomegalovirus, *toxoplasma gondii*, *mycobacterium tuberculosis*, and *Plasmodium falciparum*, among many others. Each infectious agent causes specific types of cerebral damage like cortical necrosis in the case of some viruses, infarction in bacterial meningitis, hypoxic–ischemic injury in cerebral malaria, and gliosis around calcified larvae in Neurocysticercosis; besides, they trigger an immune/inflammatory-mediated response in the infected brain tissue. The prolonged stimulation by pro-inflammatory signals, either by chronic inflammation or by seizures themselves, may lead to damage of the blood brain barrier (BBB), neuronal death, and persistent neuronal hyperexcitability. Immune responses to systemic (non-CNS) infections may result in pro-inflammatory cytokine-induced alterations in BBB integrity and subsequent neuronal hyperexcitability. Classifying an epilepsy patient as having an infectious etiology has treatment implications and thus would often take precedence over other classifications.

Metabolic etiology

The concept of a metabolic epilepsy is that it results directly from a known or presumed metabolic derangement in which seizures are a core symptom of the disorder. Someone with a transient metabolic disturbance resulting in acute-symptomatic seizures would not qualify as their seizures are provoked, and therefore they cannot be classified as epileptic (5). Several metabolic disorders result from genetic abnormalities which can manifest as cellular degeneration and dysmyelination to disorders of neuronal migration, promoting epileptogenesis indirectly by negatively impacting cellular or organ function.

These disorders are organized by the defective molecule or mechanism and categorized as small or large molecule disorders. Small-molecule disorders involve amino, organic, and fatty acids, neurotransmitters and its metabolites, urea cycle constituents, vitamins and cofactors, and they are represented by a variety of amino acidopathies, organic acidemias (e.g., methylmalonic acidemia), demyelinating conditions (e.g., Canavan disease), defective GABA metabolism (e.g., succinic semialdehyde dehydrogenase deficiency), and mitochondrial disorders (e.g., myoclonic epilepsy with ragged red fibers). Large-molecule disorders include lysosomal storage, peroxisomal and glycosylation disorders, and leukodystrophies. Even though most metabolic epilepsies will have a genetic basis, some may be acquired such as pyridoxine-dependent seizures and cerebral folate deficiency (5).

Immune etiology

An immune etiology can be suspected in patients with epilepsy of unknown origin when they are sero-

positive for neural specific antibodies and have evidence of autoimmune-mediated CNS inflammation (5). The rate of autoimmune epilepsies according to population-based studies is around 5-7% of all epilepsies. The identification of this etiology has treatment implications because epileptic seizures evoked by autoimmune encephalitis should be treated by immunotherapies instead of conventional antiepileptic drug therapies.

Autoimmune epilepsy has been linked to both neuronal cell surface antigens (LGI1, N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor (NMDA-R), α -amino-3-hydroxy-5-methyl-4-isoxazolepropionic acid (AMPA), GABA-B, and metabotropic glutamate receptor 5 (mGluR5)) and neuronal intracellular antigens (glutamic acid decarboxylase 65 (GAD65), antineuronal nuclear antibody type 1 (ANNA-1), and small cell lung carcinoma (Ma)) Autoantibodies against plasma membrane epitopes seem to impair ion channel functions, for example, IgG anti-LGI1 leads to disruption of LGI1–ADAM22 interaction which reduces synaptic AMPA receptor function, subsequently disrupting calcium influx. In a similar manner, IgG anti-NMDA-R binds to a region of the GluN1 subunit of NMDA-R disrupting the interaction between NMDA-R and ephrin type B2 receptor, accompanied by reduced synaptic NMDA-R-mediated currents. In the case of autoantibodies against intracellular epitopes, the pathogenic mechanisms seem to be mediated by cytotoxic T cells which cause neuronophagia, granzyme B neurotoxicity, neuronal loss, and gliosis, favoring epileptogenesis in the affected patients.

Immune responses are also implicated in seizure induction and in the development of epilepsy. Both innate (inflammation) and adaptive immune responses are activated in the epileptic brain by resident immune cells and their secreted-mediators, as well as for leukocytes infiltrated from the periphery. The pathogenic neuroinflammatory process can be either of peripheral, or central origin. Peripheral inflammation potentiates epileptic discharges via changes in ion and glutamate homeostasis, and also via migration of pro-inflammatory molecules from peripheral inflammatory focus to the BBB.

The pathological trigger event can be a febrile seizure, trauma, stroke or infection, any of which may lead to an inflammatory cascade that involves the activation of the IL-1 receptor/toll-like receptor (IL-1R/TLR) signaling pathways through ligation of pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) or damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), the activation of the cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) pathway, and the initiation of the transforming growth factor- β /small mothers against decapentaplegic (TGF- β /Smad) signaling cascade. The activation of glia, neurons, and endothelial cells that constitute the BBB most likely result in the release of proinflammatory cytokines, such as IL-1 β and TNF- α , and of danger signals, such as high-mobility group box-1 (HMGB1). The inflammatory mediators produced leads to BBB leakage by enhancing its permeability and upregulating leukocyte adhesion molecules on the endothelium, which acts to attract lymphocytes of the adaptive immune system leading to their infiltration into the CNS.

There is a sixth etiology category, designated as *Unknown*, reserved for patients whose etiology remains unclear.

Symptoms

Seizure symptoms vary depending on the type of seizure. Because epilepsy is caused by certain activity in the brain, seizures can affect any brain process. Seizure symptoms may include:

- Temporary confusion.
- A staring spell.
- Stiff muscles.
- Uncontrollable jerking movements of the arms and legs.
- Loss of consciousness.
- Psychological symptoms such as fear, anxiety or *deja vu*.

Sometimes people with epilepsy may have changes in their behavior. They also may have symptoms of psychosis.

Most people with epilepsy tend to have the same type of seizure each time. Symptoms are usually similar from episode to episode.

Warning signs of seizures

Some people with focal seizures have warning signs in the moments before a seizure begins. These warning signs are known as *aura*.

Warning signs might include a feeling in the stomach. Or they might include emotions such as fear. Some people might feel *deja vu*. Auras also might be a taste or a smell. They might even be visual, such as a steady or flashing light, a color, or a shape. Some people may experience dizziness and loss of balance (21). And some people may see things that aren't there, known as hallucinations.

Seizures are classified as either focal or generalized, based on how and where the brain activity causing the seizure begins.

When seizures appear to result from activity in just one area of the brain, they're called focal seizures. These seizures fall into two categories:

- **Focal seizures without loss of consciousness.** Once called simple partial seizures, these seizures don't cause a loss of awareness, also known as consciousness. They may alter emotions or change the way things look, smell, feel, taste or sound. Some people experience *deja vu*. This type of seizure also may result in involuntary jerking of a body part, such as an arm or a leg. And focal seizures may cause sensory symptoms such as tingling, dizziness and flashing lights.

- **Focal seizures with impaired awareness.** Once called complex partial seizures, these seizures involve a change or loss of consciousness. This type of seizure may seem like being in a dream. During a focal seizure with impaired awareness, people may stare into space and not respond in typical ways to the environment. They also may perform repetitive movements, such as hand rubbing, chewing, swallowing or walking in circles.

Symptoms of focal seizures may be confused with other neurological conditions, such as migraine, narcolepsy or mental illness. A thorough exam and testing are needed to tell if symptoms are the result of epilepsy or another condition.

Focal seizures may come from any lobe of the brain. Some types of focal seizures include:

- **Temporal lobe seizures.** Temporal lobe seizures begin in the areas of the brain called the temporal lobes. The temporal lobes process emotions and play a role in short-term memory. People who have these seizures often experience an *aura*. The *aura* may include sudden emotion such as fear or joy. It also may be a sudden taste or smell. Or an *aura* may be a feeling of *deja vu*, or a rising sensation in the stomach. During the seizure, people may lose awareness of their surroundings. They also may stare into space, smack their lips, swallow or chew repeatedly, or have movements of their fingers.

- **Frontal lobe seizures.** Frontal lobe seizures begin in the front of the brain. This is the part of the brain that controls movement. Frontal lobe seizures cause people to move their heads and eyes to one side. They won't respond when spoken to and may scream or laugh. They might extend one arm and flex the other arm. They also might make repetitive movements such as rocking or bicycle pedaling.

- **Occipital lobe seizures.** These seizures begin in the area of the brain called the occipital lobe. This lobe affects vision and how people see. People who have this type of seizure may have hallucinations. Or they may lose some or all of their vision during the seizure. These seizures also might cause eye blinking or make the eyes move.

Generalized seizures

Seizures that appear to involve all areas of the brain are called generalized seizures. Generalized seizures include:

- **Absence seizures.** Absence seizures, previously known as *petit mal* seizures, typically occur in children. Symptoms include staring into space with or without subtle body movements. Movements may include eye blinking or lip smacking and only last 5 to 10 seconds. These seizures may occur in clusters, happening as often as 100 times a day, and cause a brief loss of awareness.

- **Tonic seizures.** Tonic seizures cause stiff muscles and may affect consciousness. These seizures usually affect muscles in the back, arms and legs and may cause the person to fall to the ground.

- **Atonic seizures.** Atonic seizures, also known as drop seizures, cause a loss of muscle control. Since this most often affects the legs, it often causes sudden falls to the ground.

- **Clonic seizures.** Clonic seizures are associated with repeated or rhythmic jerking muscle movements. These seizures usually affect the neck, face and arms.

- **Myoclonic seizures.** Myoclonic seizures usually appear as sudden brief jerks or twitches and usually affect the upper body, arms and legs.

- **Tonic-clonic seizures.** Tonic-clonic seizures, previously known as *grand mal* seizures, are the most dramatic type of epileptic seizure. They can cause a sudden loss of consciousness and body stiffening, twitching and shaking. They sometimes cause loss of bladder control or biting of the tongue.

Differential diagnosis

There are three different types of seizures: epileptic seizures (ES), psychogenic nonepileptic seizures (PNES) and physiological nonepileptic events (22) (syncope, transient ischemic attacks, parasomnias, migraines with aura, paroxysmal extrapyramidal movement disorders, vestibular syndromes, drop attacks, hypoglycemia, panic attacks, paroxysmal sleep disorders). The main misdiagnoses of epilepsy are PNES and syncope (23). The most common misdiagnosis is PNES. PNES presents as paroxysmal signs and symptoms imitating epileptic seizures which makes it difficult to distinguish it from epileptic seizures. 10% to 15% of patients with long-term PNES turn out to additionally have epilepsy (22).

Differential diagnosis between epileptic and nonepileptic events of psychogenic and physiological origin can be done on the basis of clinical history and witness testimonies. Clinical history combined with a knowledge of seizure semiology helps in distinguishing between seizures (24).

History helps in identifying syncope and ruling out epileptic seizures. If the patient's seizure happens shortly after standing up or diaphoresis occurs before the seizure, then vasovagal syncope should be considered (25). Semiological characteristics are especially important for differentiation between ES and PNES and clinical signs.

CURRENT EPILEPSY TREATMENT

The goal of current treatment for a patient with a seizure disorder or a diagnosis of an epileptic syndrome is to enable him/her to live an unrestricted life by controlling the seizures with anti-epileptic medications, neuromodulation or surgery, avoiding precipitating factors, and addressing a variety of psychological and social issues. To date, epilepsy cannot be cured.

Pharmacological treatment

Antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) act primarily by favoring inhibition over excitation and thereby stopping or preventing the initiation or spread of seizure activity. The AEDs can be grouped according to their main mechanism of action. The mechanisms include inhibition of Na-dependent action potentials (e.g., phenytoin, carbamazepine, lamotrigine, topiramate, zonisamide, lacosamide, cenobamate), inhibition of voltage-gated Ca²⁺ channels (phenytoin), blocking of glutamate (lamotrigine, felbamate, perampanel), GABA enhancement (benzodiazepines and barbiturates), GABA reuptake inhibition (valproic acid, gabapentin, tiagabine) and opening of potassium channels (ezogabine). Two of the drugs for absence seizures, ethosuximide and valproic acid, probably act by inhibiting T-type Ca²⁺ channels in thalamic neurons (26).

Neurosurgical treatment

The current AEDs could be effective in almost 80% of individuals, the remaining 20% of patients are considered to have drug-resistant epilepsy despite efforts to find an effective combination of AEDs. These patients might benefit from removal or disconnection of a circumscribed brain region to achieve full seizure-control, or at least stop disabling seizures.

Types of neurosurgical interventions include resection procedures for lesional epilepsies caused by de-

velopmental abnormalities, tumors, vascular malformations, or trauma. For intractable temporal lobe epilepsy, temporal lobectomy with hippocampectomy remains the most common surgically treated cause of seizures. Other procedures include resections of discrete epileptogenic lesions such as tubers and certain types of tumor, resections of large parts of single or multiple lobes (partial or total lobectomy), and subtotal or total hemispherectomy for some conditions involving large portions of brain. The most common disconnection procedure involves partial and complete corpus callosotomies (27).

The effectiveness of surgical treatment depends on epilepsy type, underlying pathology, and accurate localization of the epileptogenic brain region by various clinical, neuroimaging, and neurophysiological investigations. The proportion of individuals that are seizure free after surgery ranges from 50–80% in well selected groups.

Neurostimulation

Neurostimulatory techniques are palliative options for patients with drug-resistant epilepsy when surgery is not possible or if surgery failed. Through electrical impulses applied to peripheral nerves or specific brain areas it is possible to counteract potential seizure generation or propagation. Two of the most used neurostimulation techniques, vagus nerve stimulator (VNS), the first approved neurostimulation device for epilepsy, and deep brain stimulation (DBS) using electrodes implanted into the anterior nucleus of the thalamus, have demonstrated a $\geq 50\%$ reduction in seizure frequency in at least 50% of patients in open-labelled, uncontrolled studies. VNS and DBS both are also associated with improved Quality of Life (QOL), fewer hospitalizations due to status epilepticus and reduced mortality (1, 4).

Ketogenic diet

Ketogenic diet (KD) is one which contains high fat content, low carbohydrates content and adequate protein content. This diet consists of high-fat in the form of long-chain triglycerides. As the fat metabolizes, it produces ketone bodies. The different ketone bodies, such as acetoacetate and beta hydroxybutyrate, are experimentally observed to have anticonvulsive role. Despite the new antiepileptic drugs, ketogenic diet is turning up to be a non-pharmacological substitute for treatment of epilepsy (28).

The classic ketogenic diet is one that has calculated ratio of grams of fat to grams of carbohydrates plus protein. The most feasible ratios calculated until now are 3:1 or 4:1, with about 80-90% of the energy provided by fats and 10% by carbohydrates and proteins collectively (29).

KD is most effective when taken after fasting or when the body's calorie levels are low. This is because the brain normally uses glucose as the source of energy, not fats. However, glucose levels are low in the fasting state, thus, the brain utilizes fats as the source of energy in this instance. Ketogenic diet has been used as a treatment for epileptic seizures due to its proven anticonvulsive role, and several research groups reported that KD therapy decreases the number of epileptic seizures in approximately 30-40% of children. Additionally, KD

has also been seen to be effective for infantile epileptic seizures therapy (28). It is mainly used as treatment in those patients who have DRE or for those patients who cannot undergo surgical excision procedure.

KD is not fully effective because it can cause several disorders, including but not limited to gastrointestinal disturbances and heart pathologies. Before initiating KD, the patient must be screened for disorders concerning fatty acid oxidation and metabolism.

The exact mechanism of how a ketogenic diet performs anticonvulsive activity is still unclear. However, researches have shown that it decreases threshold level of a seizure. A KD affects both neurotransmitters and the neuronal membranes when acting as an anticonvulsant.

GABA is an inhibitory neurotransmitter widely distributed in neurons. Ketogenic diets have a role in synthesizing and maintaining high levels of GABA, which may be effective in treating epileptic seizures. It is hypothesized that a KD decreases aspartate levels (induced by ketone bodies), which will facilitate the conversions of glutamate to glutamine and glutamine to GABA.

Ketogenic diet in neuronal membranes alters the vesicular glutamate transporter (VGLUTS). These are functioning by filling presynaptic vesicles and are chloride ion-dependent¹. Ketone bodies, particularly acetoacetate, competitively inhibit chloride ion channels. The exact relation between VGLUTS and KD is still unknown. This ultimately leads to an increased in the inhibitory neurotransmitter GABA, and a decreased excitatory neurotransmitter glutamate.

KD therapies have shown efficacy for epilepsy. However, in order to use ketogenic diets for treatment, the strict protocols for usage must be followed as recommended by neurologists (28). KD is in use for epilepsy and further clinical trials are being performed.

Prediction and prevention

Currently, there is no reliable non-ictal biomarker capable of tracking epileptogenesis and concurrent human acquired epilepsies with reliable accuracy and specificity. The most relevant markers are based on the EEG, particularly pathologic high-frequency oscillations (pHFOs) which are brief EEG events in the range of 100 to 600 Hertz. These are speculated to reflect summated action potentials in hyperexcitable neurons. Yet, to improve the scope of prediction and prevention (by means of reoccurrence or otherwise), further discussion on the genetic predisposition, associated and indicated comorbidities, as well as other novel biomarkers is considered relevant.

There is a strong genetic component to the occurrence of epilepsy, with estimated hundreds of genes contributing to the pathogenesis. Identification of a novel *CHRNA4* (OMIM 118504) variant in a pedigree with benign childhood epilepsy with centrotemporal spikes (BECTS) broadens the scope for prediction of at-risk subjects by means of genetic screening. Epileptogenesis is the process by which a normal brain develops epilepsy. This phase of genesis is marked by changes, mostly in neurons and glial cells, particularly in methylation of epilepsy-relevant genes *HDAC11*, *SPP1*, *GAL*, *DRD1* and *SV2C*. Furthermore, abnormal

methylation of *RASgrf1* and its subsequent downregulation has been observed in the temporal neo-cortex of epileptics. The methylation of genes coincides with the incidence of general epilepsy, whereby it serves both as a novel target for treatment and an indicator for the likelihood of seizure occurrence.

Also, under speculation is the involvement of ion channels in genetic epilepsy where an estimated 25% of genes in epilepsy code for ion channels. Hence, this furthers the claim in observed literature of the association of a hyper-excitable visuo-motor system to the development of photosensitive epilepsy. The underlying difference between photosensitive epilepsy and those without sensitivity is the decreased alpha inhibition of the visuo-motor system due to a difference in the generation of alpha oscillations by the cortical-subcortical system. Thus, the identification of the "alpha phenotype" may be useful in predicting and preventing photosensitive epileptic reoccurrences/occurrences in those that show a genetic inclination.

The mouse model of investigating post-infection (malarial) acquired epilepsy has proven useful in furthering the claim of a brain-heart interaction as a biomarker bearing relevance to epileptogenesis. On a beat to beat interval the aberrant cortical discharge precedes the change in heart activity, with this deviation from the norm being identifiable 2-14 weeks before the seizures.

Epilepsy-associated comorbidities (intellectual disability (ID), anxiety disorder and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), depression & autism spectrum disorders) may share common pathological mechanisms with epileptogenesis and in certain cases have been increasingly recognized as an early symptom of the developing epilepsy. However, they have yet to be investigated and quantified in their predictive value.

Trigger avoidance may as well be a hallmark of preventing seizures, whereby common triggers to be avoided include sleep deprivation, alcohol consumption, physical and mental exhaustion, metabolic disturbances and missed dosage of an antiepileptic drug (in treated patients). On the topic of reflex epilepsies, prevention is based on the avoidance of relevant triggers for the subject on a case by case basis. Common triggers can be external (flashing lights, hot water), internal (emotional thinking) or both. It would be advised to make informed changes in lifestyle with flickering lights, distance to screens, intensity of images and the refresh rate of television screens (a 100 Hertz television display being less liable to inducing a seizure as compared to a 50 Hertz one) in known photosensitive subjects.

Identification of biomarkers is limited by an ill-defined window of time (e.g.: EEG changes in the acute time following a traumatic insult). Genetic predispositions are unlikely to be the primary predictor, since the patients will mostly come to clinicians after onset of symptoms of seizure. A single biomarker might prove to be insufficient in predicting the epileptogenesis or a preictal period, while multiple biomarkers may be the necessary requirement.

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